
BROKEN EXPECTATIONS AND EXIT PLANS: PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT BREACH IN THE HPWS–TURNOVER INTENTION NEXUS

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DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15480426>

Abstract: High-performance work system (HPWS) are a set of HR practices aimed at cultivating high performance among the staff along with other favorable organizational and employee outcomes. In the present study, a particular employee outcome namely turnover intention is investigated with HPWS as an explanatory variable. The study also adds the psychological contract breach as another explanatory variable based on the notion that it is influenced by factors outside HPWS. The study utilized quantitative methodology and used survey as a key method of data collection. The focus of the study was selected call center from Islamabad, Pakistan (n=159). The first part of the results includes confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) which based on Cronbach alpha and Average Variance Extracted shows that our constructs had satisfactory reliability and convergent validity. Furthermore, the discriminant validity is also established using the Fornell & Larcker criteria. The path analysis result shows that HPWS dimensions including recruitment & selection ($\beta=-.0367$, $P<.05$); training & development ($\beta=-.473$, $P<.05$); promotion opportunities ($\beta=-.237$, $P<.05$); and autonomy ($\beta=-.257$, $P<.05$) exerted a negative and significant influence on staff turnover intentions. Furthermore, psychological contract breach exerts a positive and significant effect on staff turnover intention ($\beta=.234$, $P<.05$). The moderation result shows that HPWS dimensions and employee turnover intention are partially moderated by psychological contract breach. These results partially support the idea that psychological contract breach is influenced by factors beyond HPWS.

Keywords: HPWS, Psychological Contract, Breach, Turnover Intentions, Staff, Call Centre.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

High-Performance Work System (HPWS) refers to the system of HR practices designed to increase organizational effectiveness by creating conditions that help employees become highly involved in the organization and work hard to accomplish its goals (Whitener, 2001). There are a lot of studies tested the predictor and outcomes of HPWS and employee outcomes including job satisfaction (Dewi & Abadi, 2023; Zhang, He, Jiang, Luo, Li, Li, & Han, 2024); organizational commitment (Natasha, Tanuwijaya, & Gunawan, 2024; Pattnaik & Sahoo, 2023); and a reduction in turnover intention (Bakhtiar, Aziz, Sumarjan, & Kedin (2024). In the present study, we test the relationship between HPWS and its one specific outcome i.e. employee turnover intention. Accordingly, turnover intention refers to the extent to which employees plan to leave the organization (Chang, Wang, & Huang, 2013). Furthermore, we extend the HPWS and employee outcome by adding a moderator variable which is the main focus of

the study. The moderator we propose and the test is a psychological contract which refers to the staff's belief about the duties of the employer and so on (Rousseau, 1989). It is a two-way expectation between employer and employee which starts to develop from the recruitment time and continues once employee joins the organization (Hess & Jepsen, 2009). However, if the expectations of any party especially employee are not fulfilled appropriately, it may lead to dissatisfaction and a reduction in interest in work. In the present study, we test the relationship between HPWS and employee turnover intention with psychological contract as a moderator. The significance of the study is that it extends the HPWS and employee outcomes relationship thus enhancing our understanding of the process aspect of it. Furthermore, it tests the relationship in the context of call centres which is a fast-developing industry in Pakistan. By understanding the relationship between HPWS and turnover intention with the moderating role of psychological contract, we can provide useful insights as to why employees leave the organization and how it can be overcome.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are as follows;

- To test the effects of HPWS on employee turnover intention
- To test the effects of employee perceived psychological contract breach on employee turnover intention
- To test the moderating role of psychological contract breach between HPWS and employee turnover intention.

LITERATURE REVIEW

HPWS and its Dimensions

Different experts suggest different dimensions or practices related to HPWS, but we will use the common HPWS as suggested by experts including recruitment and selection, training and development, job security, promotion, communication, performance-related pay, and autonomy (McClean and Collins, 2019; Price, 2011). The brief details about these dimensions are as follows;

Recruitment & Selection

Recruitment and selection practice aims to attract and select such individuals for job openings who are suitable in terms of the skills and culture of the organization (McClean & Collins, 2019). Mostly, the literature agrees that recruitment and selection are two separate subpractices where the first one aims to attract suitable candidates for a particular opening, while, the later one focuses on using various tests and interviews to determine which candidate is suitable for the organization.

Training & Development

Training & Development practice is a planned activity or set of activities that aims to improve workforce knowledge, skills, and competencies (Iverson & Zatzick, 2007). Training & development are important for organizations to maintain a skilled and updated workforce (McClean & Collins, 2019). Furthermore, it leads to several favorable outcomes including greater employee flexibility, improved work performance, and increased commitment (Bernsen, Segers, & Tillema, 2009).

Promotion Opportunities

Promotion opportunities refer to enabling staff to progress in their career and position in the organization's hierarchy (McClellan & Collins, 2019). Internal promotion means vacancies are filled internally from the existing staff which also boosts staff morale. Whereas, lack of internal opportunities means many employees stay in their existing jobs for longer periods and thus leads to frustration and demotivation.

Job Security

The concept of job security ensures staff that their jobs are secure and their jobs will not be lost easily (McClellan & Collins, 2019). The importance of job security cannot be underscored as it is something very important for many employees especially those who are aged or when there are limited job opportunities available in the job market (Topcuoglu, Oktaysoy, Erdogan, Kaygin, & Karafakioglu, 2023).

Autonomy

Autonomy refers to the staff's capacity to make suitable decisions enabling them to perform their work adequately (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006). In other words, it is about staff discretion, freedom, and independence in decision-making. A suitable degree of autonomy is a must and can lead to improved individual and organizational performance.

Communication

Communication is about the provision of suitable information to the staff from managerial levels (Den Hartog, Boon, Verbug, & Croon, 2013). If there is good two-way communication present in the organization, it can lead to favorable staff outcomes; while a lack of good communication between management and staff results in undesirable outcomes such as poor staff-management relationship and lack of trust. So far, we have discussed briefly about the dimensions of the HPWs. Next, we discuss the relationship between the concepts for hypothesis development purposes.

The Effects of HPWS on Employee Turnover Intentions

Previous studies show that HPWS leads to several favorable employee outcomes including a reduction in turnover intention. For example, a study by Bakhtiar et al. (2024) showed that turnover intention can be predicted by HPWS. Similarly, the study by Tahir, Arul, Tummala, Shagoo, & Kutpudeen (2024) showed that HPWS dimensions significantly influence staff turnover intention in the call center context. Other studies also reported similar results including Haar, (2024); Fulmore, Fulmore, Mull, and Cooper (2023); Itzhakov, Weinstein, and Cheshin, (2023); Dodanwala and Santoso (2022); and Oh, 2020). Based on the findings of the previous studies and HPWS theory, we propose that HPWS leads to reduced turnover intention. Our sub-hypotheses are as follows;

H1a: Recruitment & selection significantly influence staff turnover intention.

H1b: Training & development significantly influence staff turnover intention.

H1c: Job security significantly influences staff turnover intention.

H1d: Promotion significantly influences staff turnover intention. H1e: Autonomy significantly influences staff turnover intention.

H1f: Communication significantly influences staff turnover intention.

Moderator Role of Psychological Contract Breach between the Relationship of HPWS and Turnover Intention

We proposed the psychological contract breach as a moderator between HPWS and turnover intention because psychological contract breach is also found to be leading to staff turnover intention (Alcover, Martínez-Iñigo, & Chambel, 2012; Bal, Kooji, & De Jong, 2013; De Hauw & De Vos, 2010; Hess & Jepsen, 2009; Marescaux, De Winne & Sels, 2013; Suazo, 2009; Zhao, Wayne, Glibkowski, & Bravo, 2007). Furthermore, in some studies, it is shown as a mediator in the proposed relationship, but we propose and test it as a moderator based on the notion that it can be influenced by factors beyond HPWS. For example, supervisory behavior, weak organizational culture, toxic work environment, and organizational politics are examples of some of the factors that can lead to a broken psychological contract. Thus, we propose the following hypothesis;

H2: Psychological contract breach significantly influences staff turnover intention.

Furthermore, for moderation, our specific hypotheses are as follows;

H3a: Psychological contract breach moderates the relationship between recruitment & selection and turnover intention.

H3b: Psychological contract breach moderates the relationship between training & development and turnover intention

H3c: Psychological contract breach moderates the relationship between job security and turnover intention.

H3d: Psychological contract breach moderates the relationship between promotion and turnover intention.

H3e: Psychological contract breach moderates the relationship between autonomy and turnover intention

H3f: Psychological contract breach moderates the relationship between communication and turnover intention

Theoretical Framework

To develop the theoretical framework, we utilized two theories. The first theory is signaling theory in the context of HRM which suggests that employees perceive HR practices and policies as a signal from the employer about what is being valued in the organization (Casper & Harris, 2008). If an organization's HR practices are based on giving value to the staff, it provides a positive signal to the employees and results in favorable outcomes. On the other hand, if HR practices are perceived as negative, exploitative, or coercive in nature, it will send a negative signal and have negative outcomes. The second theory we used for constructing our theoretical model is the social exchange theory which while applying to the HR context states that economic and social exchange are part of a normal employer-employee relationship (Snape & Redman, 2010). Accordingly, in the employer-employee relationship, economic exchanges are fixed such as salary, bonuses, and other incentives; whereas, social exchanges are less formalized and depend on the reciprocity norms (Snape & Redman, 2010; Tzafrir, 2005). It means that in social exchange, if employees feel that the employer is taking care of

them, they will try to reciprocate the same and vice versa. HPWS practices can provide important signals to employees about how employees are treated in an organization (signaling theory) and encourage employees to provide suitable returns to the employer (social exchange theory). Thus, we argue that HPWS can foster a positive psychological contract and in return reduce employee turnover intention. On the other hand, if HPWS is weak, it may lead to a psychological contract breach and increased turnover intentions. Based on these two theories and the arguments mentioned, we propose the following theoretical model.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework of the Study

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilizes a cross-sectional survey-based design. It is cross-sectional because we collected data only once. Furthermore, it is quantitative and explanatory in nature. It is explanatory since we attempt to explain the relationship between independent and dependent variables.

Population and Sampling

The focus of the study is call center employees in Islamabad which makes the population. Since the population is large and inaccessible, we used convenience random sampling which is also a limitation of the study. A total of 300 were distributed out of which we got 159 usable surveys making a response rate of 53%.

Research Tools

The survey is based on adapted measures. The construct of HPWS is adapted from Kehoe and Wright (2013) where each dimension of HPWS is measured by 4 items. Psychological contract breach is adapted from Robinson and Morrison, (2000) and consists of 5 items. Turnover intention is measured by 4 items and adapted from O'Reilly Chatman, and Caldwell (1991).

Data Collection

The primary data is collected through the survey. The survey was distributed in selected Call centers where management gave formal permission to conduct the study. Once collected, the data is checked for inconsistencies and entered into the system for further analysis.

RESULTS

Demographic Information

Table 1

Demographic Details of the Participants

	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	111	69.8%
Female	48	30.2%
Age		
18 to 25 Years	45	28.3%
25 to 40 Years	106	66.7%
Above 40 Years	8	5.0%

Source: Study Survey

N=159

In terms of demographics, gender-wise, male (69.8%) participation was more compared to female (30.2%). Age-wise, the biggest age category who participated in the survey was 25 to 40 years (66.7%); followed by younger individuals (28.3%).

Measurement Model

The confirmatory factor analysis using AMOS version 28 was performed to test the reliability and convergent validity. The results are as follows;

Table 2

Construct Reliability and Convergent Validity

Construct	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Recruitment & Selection	.854	.853	.627
Training & Development	.773	.776	.632
Job Security	.816	.813	.607
Promotion	.749	.753	.719
Autonomy	.823	.824	.635
Communication	.759	.753	.725
Psychological Contract Breach	.743	.740	.693
Turnover Intentions	.825	.827	.639

The result shows that all constructs had Cronbach alpha and composite reliability of above 0.70 which is an indicator of internal consistency and satisfactory reliability. The cut-of value for Cronbach alpha and Composite Reliability is above 0.70 as suggested by experts (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016; Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Gudergan, 2017). Furthermore, all AVE are greater than 0.50 so it shows that the constructs had good convergent validity. (values suggested by Hair et al. 2017).

For testing discriminant validity, we used the Fornell & Larcker (1981) suggested criteria. Accordingly, if in the table 3, the values are inter-variable correlation while the diagonal bold values are the square root of AVE. The criteria suggest that diagonal bold values should be greater than other numbers in its respective rows and column which is satisfied in our data. Thus, we can say that discriminant validity is established for our data.

Table 3
Discriminant Validity

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
								Recruitment & Selection
0.792								
Training		0.623						
Development			0.795					
Job Security	0.349	0.324	0.779					
Promotion	0.305	0.184	0.379	0.848				
Autonomy	0.415	0.346	0.428	0.311	0.797			
Communication	0.315	0.676	0.446	0.535	0.635	0.851		
Psychological Contract	0.416	0.485	0.579	0.673	0.613	0.535	0.832	
Breach								
Turnover Intentions	0.634	0.547	0.511	0.527	0.607	0.713	0.737	0.799

Table 4
Hypotheses Testing

H.No.	Path	Coefficient	S.E.	T-stat	P-Value	Remarks
H1a	R&S > TI	-0.367	0.079	-4.646	.001	Supported
H1b	T&D > TI	-0.473	0.081	-5.840	.000	Supported
H1c	JS > TI	-0.057	0.083	-0.687	.344	Not Supported
H1d	Pr > TI	-0.237	0.075	-3.160	.001	Supported

H1e	Au > TI	-0.257	0.121	-2.124	.002	Supported
H1f	Co > TI	-0.123	0.116	-	1.060	.235 Not Supported
H2	PCB > TI	0.234	0.067	3.493	.001	Supported
H3a	R&S X PCB > TI	-0.057	0.024	-	2.388	.031 Supported
H3b	T&D X PCB > TI	-0.048	0.032	-1.497	.138	Not Supported
H3c	JS X PCB > TI	-0.060	0.024	-	2.483	.043 Supported
H3d	Pr X PCB > TI	-0.073	0.028	-	2.607	.042 Supported
H3e	Au X PCB > TI	-0.043	0.032	-1.344	.193	Not Supported
H3f	Co X PCB > TI	-0.045	0.021	-2.141	.047	Supported

The result shows that four out of six HPWS dimensions had negative and significant influence on turnover intentions including recruitment & selection ($\beta = -.0367$, $P < .05$); training & development ($\beta = -.473$, $P < .05$); promotion opportunities ($\beta = -.237$, $P < .05$); and autonomy ($\beta = .257$, $P < .05$). Whereas, the results for job security ($\beta = -.057$, $P > .05$); and communication ($\beta = .123$, $P > .05$) turned out to be insignificant. The result also shows that psychological contract breach has positive and significant effects on staff turnover intention ($\beta = .234$, $P < .05$). For moderation analysis, the result shows that four out of six hypothesized moderating paths turned out to be negative and significant. The significant moderating relationship included recruitment & selection ($\beta = -.057$, $P < .05$); job security ($\beta = -.060$,

$P < .05$); promotion ($\beta = -.073$, $P < .05$); and communication ($\beta = -.045$, $P < .05$). Based on these results, we accept H1a, H1b, H1d, H1e, H2, H3a, H3c, H3d, H3f.

Discussion

The objective of the study was to test a model based on HPWS and turnover intentions with the moderating role of psychological contract breach. The result shows that HPWS dimensions negatively influence the staff turnover intention. The results are consistent with the findings of previous studies which show that HPWS influences staff turnover intentions such as Bakhtiar et al. (2024); Tahir, Arul, Tummala, Shagoo, and Kutpudeen, (2024); Tahir (2022); Dodanwala and Santoso (2022); Itzchakov et al., (2023); Fulmore et al. (2023); Haar (2024) and so on. The results are consistent with the social exchange theory and accordingly, if organization invests in its HPWS practices, it will oblige employees to perform well and stay with the organization in return. The results are consistent with the signaling theory since HPWS sends important signal to staff that the employer is giving higher value to the staff which results in favorable outcomes including a reduction in staff turnover. The other major finding of the study is that staff perceived psychological contract breach leads to staff turnover intention. These findings are also consistent with the previous findings including Bal et al. (2013); Alcover et al. (2012); Marescaux et al. (2013) and so on. This is because if employees perceive that the employer is not taking care of its staff and not fulfilling its responsibility, it leads to a broken psychological contract which leads to a higher turnover intention as staff tends to withdraw from the situation. The moderating relationship shows that HPWS influences staff turnover intention while psychological contract breach moderates the relationship. In other words, it shows that staff turnover intentions can be further enhanced if psychological contract breach exists and in this situation, HPWS will not be enough to stop turnover intention. The findings of the present study add to the literature on HPWS and turnover intention and make a contribution by adding a moderator in the relationship. By proposing and testing psychological contract breach as a moderator, it enhances our understanding of the nature of dynamics in the HPWS and employee outcome relationship.

CONCLUSION

The objective of the study was to test the effects of HPWS on employee turnover intentions with the moderating role of psychological contract breach. The result of the study shows that HPWS dimensions partially influence turnover intention. Furthermore, the psychological contract breach not only influences the staff turnover intention but also works as a moderator. The results are significant since it show that HPWS not only directly influences staff-level outcomes; as there are other variables that interfere with the relationship. By testing the psychological contract breach as a moderator, we showed that HPWS and staff outcome is not a simple linear relationship; as it is more complex and needs more rigorous analysis in the future. Furthermore, it shows that psychological contract breaches can be investigated separately and is influenced by factors beyond HPWS.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made.

- Call centers need to give greater attention to HPWS. For example, more efforts should be made for recruitment as well as for developing the staff. A greater autonomy and more two-way communication should be encouraged between staff and the management. Since job security is a major factor in HPWS, so it should also be focused by the call center.
- The leadership of the call centre should foster a culture of security and psychological safety so staff can work in an efficient way and can forward their suggestions/feedback to the management. Such culture will also encourage creativity and entrepreneurship in the call center context.
- The management of the call center should focus on developing a healthy and positive psychological contract relationship between staff and management. If psychological contract is strong, it will enable getting suitable employee outcomes based on HPWS.
- Staff turnover should be monitored, investigated using exit interviews as well as other means. Efforts should be made to decrease the turnover.

Limitations of the Study

The limitations of the study include a relatively small sample size and cross-sectional data collected through a survey. The convenience random sampling for sample selection also remains a limitation of the study. Collection of data based on staff perception is also a limitation as such data is subject to memory and misrepresentation. A future researcher may investigate the HPWS and staff turnover intentions with more diverse moderating variables as well as the use of demographic in the relationship to further understand the relationship.

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